

NEW SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF FORMALDEHYDE

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Formaldehyde reacts with sulphanilic acid in the pH range of 1.2 to 1.5 to afford a deep wine-red, water-soluble compound with an absorption peak at 480 m μ . This has been made the basis of a new, rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method of estimating formaldehyde. The system obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 9 to 65 mg. of formaldehyde per 100 c.c. of solution. The sensitivity of colour reaction, determined in Nessler's cylinders, is one part of formaldehyde in 40,000 parts of solution. The ratio of two reactants has been determined to be 1:1. The molecular extinction coefficient at 480 m μ has been determined to be 32.15, and dissociation constant at 25° to be 3.69×10^{-3} .

In a preliminary experiment it was observed that on heating formaldehyde and sulphanilic acid at low pH, a deep wine-red, water-soluble compound was formed. It is very stable and the colour intensity does not change even after 24 hours on keeping. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to use this reaction for the spectrophotometric determination of formaldehyde. Different acids were used for adjusting the pH, and sulphuric acid was found to provide slightly better results. Time of heating affects the colour intensity, and the optimum period has been found to be between 15 and 25 minutes. The molar ratio of formaldehyde to sulphanilic acid for constant maximum absorption has been found to be 1:3. The ratio of the two reactants, in the formation of coloured compound, found by using Job's method of continued variations, has been determined to be 1:1.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard formaldehyde solution was prepared by determining the strength of formalin volumetrically, using hydrogen peroxide and diluting it to provide $10^{-3}M$, 3 mg./c.c. and 4 mg./c.c. solutions.

On account of the insolubility of sulphanilic acid in water, its sodium salt was prepared and a 5% (w/v) solution in water was used. 2.5% H_2SO_4 (v/v) was used for adjusting the pH.

A Bausch and Lomb 'Spectronic-20' was used for measuring the absorption, using 1 cm cuvettes. pH measurements were made with a Beckman pH meter (model H-2). Visual colour comparisons were made with 50 c.c. Nessler's cylinders.

Spectral Characteristics.—Formaldehyde solution (8 c.c.) containing 4 mg./c.c. was

taken in a 100 c.c. conical flask and 10 c.c. of 5% (w/v) sodium sulphanilate solution and 10 c.c. of 2.5% (v/v) H_2SO_4 were added. The contents of the flask were heated on a boiling water-bath for about 20 minutes. It was cooled and made up to 100 c.c. in a volumetric flask. *pH* of this solution was 1.5 and the concentration of formaldehyde was 32 mg./100 c.c. Absorption was measured at different wave-lengths using water as blank. Fig. 1 shows the spectral characteristics of formaldehyde-sulphanilic acid compound. The absorption peak is at 480 mμ.

Heating Time.—Several samples were prepared as described above, using 6 c.c. of formaldehyde solution containing 3 mg./c.c.

These were heated on a boiling water-bath for periods varying from 5 to 35 minutes, cooled and made up to 100 c.c. Absorption was measured at 480 mμ. Fig. 2 shows that absorption is maximum between 15 and 25 minutes of heating. The time of heating in all subsequent experiments was kept at 20 minutes.

Effect of *pH*.—Solutions containing the same amount of formaldehyde (7 c.c. of 4 mg./c.c.) and 5% sodium sulphanilate (10 c.c.) and varying amounts of 2.5% H_2SO_4 were prepared so that *pH* after dilution ranged between 1.0 and 2.0. Remaining procedure was the same as described above. The range of constant maximum absorption is between *pH* 1.2 and 1.5 (Fig. 3), which corresponds to *pH* 0.6 and 0.9 respectively before dilution. The colour intensity decreases with the increase of *pH* and the solution becomes almost colorless beyond *pH* 4.2.

Reagent Concentration and Mole Ratio.—A series of solutions was prepared at about *pH* 1.3 with a constant concentration of formaldehyde at $9 \times 10^{-3} M$ and keeping formaldehyde to sodium sulphanilate ratio between 2:1 and 2:10. Fig. 4 shows the ratio of formaldehyde to sodium sulphanilate for constant maximum absorption as 1:3.

Stability of Colour.—A sample was prepared, as noted above, and absorption was measured at different intervals of time. There was no change in absorption reading taken even after 24 hours.

Beer's Law.—Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of formaldehyde between 9 and 65 mg. per 100 c.c. of solution. Molecular extinction coefficient at 480 $m\mu$ was found to be 32.35.

Sensitivity of Reaction.—Sensitivity of the reaction was determined in Nessler's cylinder in the usual way after preparing the solutions as described above. It was found to be 1 of formaldehyde in 40,000 parts of solution.

Procedure.—A sample of formalin containing 10 to 60 mg. of formaldehyde was taken in a 100 c.c. conical flask and 10 c.c. of 5% (w/v) sodium sulphanilate and 10 c.c. of 2.5% (v/v) H_2SO_4 were added. The final pH after dilution should be between 1.2 and 1.5. The contents were heated on a boiling water-bath for 20 minutes, cooled and transferred into a 100 c.c. volumetric flask and filled up to the mark with distilled water. Absorbance was measured at 480 $m\mu$, using water as blank. Other aldehydes interfere in the determination of formaldehyde by developing a similar but very light colour.

Formula of the Coloured Compound.—The molar ratio of formaldehyde to sulphanic acid in the formation of the coloured compound was investigated by using Job's method of continued variations (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113). The final concentration of formaldehyde was varied between $2 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $18 \times 10^{-4} M$ and pH was kept at about 1.4. Fig. 5 shows the curves obtained by applying this method. The maxima at 0.5 mole fraction reagent indicates the ratio of the two reactants as 1 : 1.

FIG. 5

DISCUSSION

The dissociation of the coloured compound in solution may be written as:

where α is the degree of dissociation and C is the concentration of the coloured compound. The dissociation constant K is given by the equation

$$K = \frac{(\alpha C)^2}{(1-\alpha)C} = \frac{\alpha^2 C}{1-\alpha}$$

The value of α may be obtained from Fig. 4 by the following relationship :

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m} = \frac{49 - 26}{49} = 0.47,$$

where E_m is the maximum absorption obtained from the horizontal portion of the curve, when all the formaldehyde is present in the form of coloured compound, and E_s is the observed absorption at the stoichiometric molar ratio of formaldehyde to sulphanilic acid. The concentration C of the coloured compound is equal to the total concentration of formaldehyde, which is $9 \times 10^{-3}M$. By substituting these values in the above equation, the value of K at 25° comes to 3.69×10^{-3} and the stability constant K' is equal to 2.69×10^3 .

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